

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA
Dr. Kuldeep Kaur
Assistant Professor of Economics A.S.B.A.S.J.S. Memorial College Bela (Rupnagar)
Abstract :

The sustainable development in India can be defined as the practice of maintaining productivity by replacing used resources with resources of equal or greater value without degrading or endangering natural biotic systems. Sustainable development binds together concern for the carrying capacity of natural systems with the social, political and economic challenges faced by humanity. Sustainability science is the study of the concepts of sustainable development and environmental science. There is an emphasis on the present generations' responsibility to regenerate, maintain and improve planetary resources for use by future generations. It is an attempt to examine the sustainable development goals such as eliminate poverty, erase hunger, establish good health and well being, provide quality education, enforce gender equality, improve clean water and sanitation, grow affordable and clean energy, create decent work and economic growth, increase industry, innovation and infrastructure, reduce inequality, mobile sustainable cities and communities, influence climate action, develop life below water, advance life on land, guarantee peace, justice and strong institutions and build partnerships for the goals.

The study is based on secondary data collected from books, journals and internet etc. There are seventeen goals which covers entire sustainable development in India. The main findings of the study are the variation is found according to seventeen goals such as 1. No Poverty 2. Zero Hunger 3. Good Health & Well Being 4. Quality Education, 5 Gender Equality, 6 Clean water & Sanitation 7. Affordable & Clean Energy, 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, 9 Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure, 10 Reduce Inequalities, 11 Sustainable Cities And Communities, 12 Ensure sustainable consumption and Production Patterns, 13 Climate Action, 14 Life Below Water, 15 Life on Land And 16 Peace, Justice & Strong Institution.

Key words: *Sustainable development, Natural systems, Sustainability science, Present Generations Responsibility*

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Introduction :

The origin of the sustainable development has its roots in ideas about sustainable forest management, which were developed in Europe during the period of 17th and 18th centuries. In response to a growing awareness of the

depletion of timber resources in England, John Evelyn argued, in his 1662 essay *Sylva* that “sowing and planting of trees had to be regarded as a national duty of every landowner, in order to stop the destructive over-exploitation of natural resources” and In 1713, Hans Carl von Carlowitz, a senior mining administrator in the service of Elector Frederick Augustus I of Saxony published *Sylvicultura economica*, a 400-page work on forestry. Building upon the ideas of Evelyn and French minister Jean-Baptiste Colbert, von Carlowitz developed the concept of managing forests for sustained yield. His work influenced others, including Alexander von Humboldt and Georg Ludwig Hartig, eventually leading to the development of the science of forestry. This, in turn, influenced people like Gifford Pinchot, the first head of the US Forest Service, whose approach to forest management was driven by the idea of wise use of resources and Aldo Leopold whose land ethic was influential in the development of the environmental movement in the 1960s.

The first time uses of the term sustainable in the contemporary sense was by the Club of Rome in 1972 in its classic report on the Limits to Growth, written by a group of scientists led by Dennis and Donella Meadows of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. In 1980s the International Union for Conservation of Nature published a world conservation strategy that included one of the first references to sustainable development as a global priority and introduced the term “sustainable development” and two years later, the United Nations World Charter for Nature raised five principles of conservation by which human conduct affecting nature is to be guided and judged. In 1987s the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development released the report *Our Common Future*, commonly called the Brundtland Report. The report included what is now one of the most widely recognized definitions of sustainable development.

Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It contains within it two key concepts such as

1. The concept of ‘needs’, in particular, the essential needs of the world’s poor, to which overriding priority should be given; and
2. The idea of limitations imposed by the state of technology and social organization on the environment’s ability to meet present and future needs.

World Commission on Environment and Development, *Our Common Future* (1987)

Since the Brundtland Report, the concept of sustainable development has developed beyond the initial intergenerational framework to focus more on the goal of “socially inclusive and environmentally sustainable economic growth”. In 1992, the UN Conference on Environment and Development published the Earth Charter, which outlines the building of a just, sustainable, and peaceful global society in the 21st century. The action plan Agenda 21 for sustainable development identified information, integration, and participation as key building blocks to help countries achieve development that recognizes these interdependent pillars. Its main emphasizes that in sustainable development, everyone is a user and provider of information. Sustainable development including economic development, social development and environmental protection. In broadly sense defined “sustainable development is a systems approach to growth and development and to manage natural, produced,

and social capital for the welfare of their own and future generations”. The term of sustainable development as used by the United Nations incorporates both issues associated with land development and broader issues of human development such as education, public health, and standard of living etc. It includes four interconnected domains: ecology, economics, politics and culture.

Sustainable development in India encompasses a variety of development schemes in social, cleantech such as clean energy, clean water and sustainable agriculture and human resources segments, having caught the attention of both Central and State governments and also public and private sectors. Sustainable development defined as ‘A sustainable society is one in which peoples’ ability to do what they have good reason to value is continually enhanced’ Sen, 1990.

Objectives :

The main objectives of the study are following.

1. It is an attempt to examine the sustainable development in India.
2. To examine the State wise sustainable development in India.
3. To examine the UT wise sustainable development in India.
4. It is an attempt to examine the sustainable development goals such as eliminate poverty, erase hunger, establish good health and well being, provide quality education, enforce gender equality, improve clean water and sanitation, grow affordable and clean energy, create decent work and economic growth, increase industry, innovation and infrastructure, reduce inequality, mobile sustainable cities and communities, influence climate action, develop life below water, advance life on land, guarantee peace, justice and strong institutions and build partnerships for the goal.

Methodology :

The study is based on Secondary data collected from Niti Ajog Report, books, journals and internet etc. There are 28 states and 9 UTs in India which covers entire country of India and there are seventeen goals which cover entire sustainable development in India. The main findings of the study are the variation is found according to seventeen goals such as 1. No Poverty 2. Zero Hunger 3. Good Health & Well Being 4. Quality Education, 5 Gender Equality, 6 Clean water & Sanitation 7. Affordable & Clean Energy, 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, 9 Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure, 10 Reduce Inequalities, 11 Sustainable Cities And Communities, 12 Ensure sustainable consumption and Production Patterns, 13 Climate Action, 14 Life Below Water, 15 Life on Land And 16 Peace, Justice & Strong Institution.

Data Analysis :

The table 1 reveals that there are seventeen goals such as 1 No Poverty, 2 Zero Hunger, 3 Good Health & Well Being, 4 Quality Education, 5 Gender Equality, 6 Clean Water & Sanitation 7. Affordable & Clean Energy, 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, 9 Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure, 10 Reduce Inequalities, 11 Sustainable

Cities And Communities, 12 Ensure sustainable consumption and Production Patterns, 13 Climate Action, 14 Life Below Water, 15 Life on Land 16 Peace, Justice & Strong Institutions. The score is Achiever (100), Front Runner (65-99), Performer (50-64) and Aspirant (0-49). The table also shows that the state wise performance across SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals)

Table 1: State wise Performance Across SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals)

Sr no.	States	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	Composite
1	Kerala	83	80	72	80	63	89	100	62	60	69	75	65	69	53	77	80	75
2	Himachal Pradesh	80	52	78	80	62	85	100	78	61	78	79	77	62	-	68	73	74
3	Tamil Nadu	86	66	81	69	59	87	100	71	71	74	79	78	61	11	63	71	74
4	Andhra Pradesh	81	52	77	50	58	92	100	67	52	74	78	84	63	79	69	77	72
5	Goa	83	78	72	71	55	100	100	76	68	75	89	47	44	50	59	62	72
6	Karnataka	68	53	78	64	57	85	100	66	64	67	78	89	62	60	67	76	72
7	Uttarakhand	74	61	77	70	46	85	100	63	56	77	76	82	60	-	64	86	72
8	Sikkim	80	69	62	58	58	89	100	71	52	61	85	76	65	-	73	72	71
9	Maharashtra	66	44	83	64	51	90	100	62	66	71	87	82	58	57	52	69	70
10	Gujarat	66	46	86	52	49	93	94	64	72	64	87	50	67	57	61	82	69
11	Telangana	68	50	67	63	41	96	100	73	59	67	76	73	43	-	81	71	69
12	Mizoram	80	72	79	60	54	85	100	51	32	64	61	87	66	-	48	81	68
13	Punjab	69	73	77	60	45	66	100	57	69	68	91	71	51	-	48	76	68
14	Haryana	69	58	72	64	43	80	100	59	66	68	81	77	51	-	48	71	67
15	Tripura	82	52	67	42	39	82	83	57	35	85	67	99	41	-	69	80	65
16	Manipur	60	64	68	63	41	87	96	36	35	70	65	89	57	-	60	69	64
17	Madhya Pradesh	44	43	62	45	55	88	86	60	37	51	81	78	49	-	84	66	62
18	West Bengal	59	46	76	54	41	81	98	57	53	71	45	79	39	50	53	81	62
19	Chhattisgarh	49	37	60	55	64	89	78	64	38	72	78	64	38	-	65	71	61
20	Nagaland	73	64	61	39	48	87	69	48	30	96	48	91	69	-	63	79	61
21	Odisha	41	42	67	45	46	86	80	48	46	66	70	73	70	82	83	59	61
22	Arunachal Pradesh	54	66	64	41	37	67	85	50	31	69	39	77	58	-	93	64	60

23	Meghalaya	77	37	70	48	51	75	50	63	25	88	51	73	62	-	64	72	60
24	Rajasthan	63	53	70	60	39	54	100	57	45	45	81	74	49	-	43	73	60
25	Uttar Pradesh	44	41	60	51	50	83	100	53	42	41	77	79	39	-	61	79	60
26	Assam	51	41	59	43	25	64	98	50	39	65	55	66	53	-	78	62	57
27	Jharkhand	36	19	74	45	51	83	77	54	37	65	71	55	25	-	71	70	66
28	Bihar	32	31	66	29	48	91	78	50	24	48	67	59	16	-	62	73	52

Source: NITI AJOG REPORT 2019-20

The table 2 shows that there are seventeen goals such as 1 No Poverty, 2 Zero Hunger, 3 Good Health & Well Being, 4 Quality Education, 5 Gender Equality, 6 Clean water & Sanitation, 7 Affordable & Clean Energy, 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, 9 Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure, 10 Reduce Inequalities, 11 Sustainable Cities And Communities, 12 Ensure sustainable consumption and Production Patterns, 13 Climate Action, 14 Life Below Water, 15 Life on Land And is shown in table 1. The score is Achiever (100), Front Runner (65-99), Performer (50-64) and Aspirant (0-49). The table also shows that the UT wise performance across SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals)

Table 2: UT Wise Performance across SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals)

Sr no.	UT	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	Composite
1	Andaman and Nicobar Island	71	45	68	57	68	87	100	59	23	67	85	73	77	-	72	46	67
2	Chandigarh	75	97	74	79	58	99	100	70	45	100	98	78	61	-	85	73	79
3	Darda & Nagar Haveli	65	27	80	56	53	95	71	57	47	66	89	62	18	-	62	75	62
4	Daman and Diu	65	27	80	56	53	95	71	57	47	66	89	62	18	-	62	75	62
5	Delhi	81	63	90	75	33	61	100	65	66	72	65	50	55	-	81	62	68
6	Jammu & Kashmir	69	71	70	49	46	88	100	47	42	65	57	95	63	-	52	74	66
7	Ladakh	79	71	70	49	46	84	100	59	48	65	57	95	66	-	27	74	66
8	Lakshadweep	61	74	78	62	58	100	83	62	40	75	56	63	68	-	67	77	68
9	Puducherry	75	59	70	70	66	91	98	68	59	62	76	66	23	-	50	86	68

Source: NITI AJOG REPORT 2019-20

Findings :

The main findings of the study are the variation is found according to seventeen goals such as 1. No Poverty 2. Zero Hunger 3. Good Health & Well Being 4. Quality Education, 5 Gender Equality, 6 Clean water & Sanitation 7. Affordable & Clean Energy, 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, 9 Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure, 10 Reduce Inequalities, 11 Sustainable Cities And Communities, 12 Ensure sustainable consumption and Production Patterns, 13 Climate Action, 14 Life Below Water, 15 Life on Land And 16 Peace, Justice & Strong Institution.

Suggestion:

The government should take steps for achieving these goals and providing financial resources, making policies etc. The financing needs for these SDG investments are far greater than the fiscal space available to the governments of low-income developing countries (LIDCs). To achieve the SDGs, the LIDCs will need a significant increase in fiscal space, which will require a combination of domestic and global fiscal policies.

Conclusion:

The sustainable development goals such as eliminate poverty, erase hunger, establish good health and well being, provide quality education, enforce gender equality, improve clean water and sanitation, grow affordable and clean energy, create decent work and economic growth, increase industry, innovation and infrastructure, reduce inequality, mobile sustainable cities and communities, influence climate action, develop life below water, advance life on land, guarantee peace, justice and strong institutions and build partnerships for the goals.

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